

NOAO: Rest in Peace

Sidney Wolff, AURA

I first came to the national observatory in 1984, just a year after John Jefferies was appointed as the first director of National Optical Astronomy Observatories, which then included KPNO, CTIO, and the National Solar Observatory (NSO). After retiring several times, I am now back at the national observatory working on the US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP) and witnessing the creation of NSF's NOIRLab. In a sense, then, I have observed nearly the entire lifetime of NOAO.

I originally decided to come to NOAO because I had experienced the thrill and the satisfaction that comes from building an observatory from the ground up. When I went to Hawai'i in 1967, there were no telescopes on Mauna Kea. (The name was two words in those days—now Maunakea is preferred.) When I left Hawai'i, the CFHT, IRTF, and UKIRT were all in operation, along with the 88-inch and two 24-inch telescopes, and Mauna Kea had been chosen as the site for the Keck Observatory. I thought that transferring to the national observatory offered me the best opportunity to continue building new telescopes and new observatories.

And build we did: WIYN, SOAR, the two Gemini telescopes, and LSST (now Vera C. Rubin Observatory) are some of the legacies of NOAO. Prior to the advent of NOAO, most of the construction at the national observatories was funded by NSF. The telescopes that we built at NOAO required unprecedented forms of partnerships. WIYN and SOAR were both projects carried out with universities, and SOAR also involved Brazil. The Gemini telescopes were carried out by an international partnership, and LSST by NSF and DOE working together. These new types of partnerships were key to expanding the capabilities offered by the national observatory.

I am proud not only of the telescopes that we built but also of the many people who gained experience at NOAO that allowed them to go on to leadership positions with other organizations. I would include in this list (in alphabet-

ical order) Taft Armandroff, Todd Boroson, Richard Green, Buell Jannuzi, Matt Mountain, Jim Oschmann, Pat Osmer, Mark Phillips, Caty Pilachowski, Dave Silva, and Bob Williams. (I apologize to anyone that I may have left off this list.) Of course, much of our home-grown talent remains within the organization and is key to its current strength.

During my tenure as Director, I managed to build relationships between Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) and Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO) that allowed us to change our name to National Optical Astronomy Observatory (singular instead of plural), and NSO became independent. My biggest disappointment came when the decision was made to separate Gemini cleanly from NOAO. In my opinion, that decision was not to the long-term advantage of either organization. I am therefore very pleased to see that finally CTIO, KPNO, Gemini, and the Rubin Observatory are joining together to form a true national laboratory for ground-based astronomy. As Director of AURA's portion of the US-ELTP, I can already see the advantages. Now I can go anywhere in the organization to find the expertise needed to formulate a compelling proposal for the services that we will provide to users of GMT and TMT. TAC upgrades being carried out in Tucson, the Phase I and Phase II observing tools and the adaptive/dynamic queue scheduling system being modernized and automated by Gemini, and the plans for a unified archive by the Astro Data Lab will form the basis for services that we will provide to enable access to GMT, TMT, and to the data from both telescopes. I am also drawing on Rubin expertise in how to manage the large software project that we are planning.

From my point of view, unification of the various ground-based observatories managed by AURA has been slow in coming, but it has arrived just in time to meet the challenges of the future. We simply could not prepare the proposal for our portion of the US-ELTP without access to the expertise available in CSDC, Gemini, and Rubin.

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Sidney Wolff, with the telescopes on Cerro Pachón in Chile (from left to right): SOAR, Gemini South, the calibration telescope for the Legacy Survey of Space and Time, and the Vera C. Rubin Observatory.